

CREATIVITY OF AMERICAN WRITERS OF THE SECOND HALF OF THE 20TH CENTURY IN THE CONTEXT OF THE SOUTHERN LITERARY TRADITION

Sobirjonova Oydina Rasuljon kizi

Teacher of English at school No. 10, Yangi-Kurgan district

Abstract. This paper examines the evolution of US literary output in terms of four factors relating to its main authors: their geographic location and migration patterns over almost two centuries, the links between their literary output and age, variations by genre and gender, and motivations for location, especially in New York.

Keywords: literary output, location, migration, age, gender.

INTRODUCTION

By 1950, however, traditional aesthetic innovation was wearing thin. The United States had endured the Great Depression, a long decade of hardship that not only dampened the promise of the American dream but changed literary methods to a surprising extent. The amalgam of cryptic modernist innovation and almost sentimental proselytizing that characterized the collective, proletarian novel and the speech-lined poems of the Depression gave rise to incredible variety: despite the paper shortages of World War II, published writing in the United States continued to be influential. It is in the aftermath of the war, once people had righted their perceptions about causation and blame, and had admitted again the atrocity of war itself (as well as of the Holocaust and the atomic bomb), that literature — whether called contemporary or postmodern — began to change.

The above implies that not only are the issues looked at in this paper of interest in themselves, especially in terms of the modern debate about creative clusters (see Andersson et al, 2014, Kuld and O'Hagan, 2019, and Wojan et al, 2007) but may also inform in some small way a better understanding of the artistic dimensions to the output of US writers. The paper examines the evolution of US literary output in terms of four factors relating to almost

five hundred of its main authors born between 1800 and 1949: their geographic location and migration patterns, the links between their literary output and age, variations by genre and gender, and motivations for location, especially in New York.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

As outlined in Kuld and O'Hagan (2019) an interest in the location and clustering of creative workers goes back a long time, with the first economic analysis as such dating perhaps to Marshall (1890). The more recent literature on clustering as they point out relates more to creative industries, not creative individuals, with some exceptions such as those listed above.

For this study, we have constructed a yearly data set on the 483 US writers listed in *Encyclopedia Britannica* born between 1800 to 1949. The US as a nation changed dramatically in the 19th and early 20th century, especially in terms of physical boundaries and means of transport. This impacted not only the nature of US literature over the period but also the four factors of interest here in relation to US authors. Section 2 provides a broad coverage of this background, concentrating mainly on the most well-known authors in terms of their geographic location, involvement in publishing and sources of income. This adds not only 'faces and colour' to the later statistical analysis but also provides an insight into what patterns to look for in this analysis. The section also outlines briefly the changes in transport, publishing and population size alluded to above.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Like other national literatures, American literature was shaped by the history of the country that produced it. For almost a century and a half, America was merely a group of colonies scattered along the eastern seaboard of the North American continent. After a successful rebellion against the motherland, America became the United States, a nation. By the end of the 19th century this nation extended southward to the Gulf of Mexico, northward to the 49th parallel, and westward to the Pacific.

The poet Ezra Pound (1885-1972) also spent much of his adult life in Europe and was greatly influenced by other creative movements there at the time. He had a major

influence on other poets, including T.S. Eliot (1888-1965), who won the Nobel Prize for Literature in 1948; he also moved to Europe, to live in England aged 25.

Scott Fitzgerald (1896-1940) spent most of his youth in New York and then New Jersey, when he attended Princeton University. Fitzgerald dropped out of Princeton though and enlisted in the US Army in 1917 on the brink of World War I. He became an officer, married, and after being decommissioned, went to New York City to pursue his literary career. *This Side of Paradise* was his first successful novel, allowing him to travel extensively in Paris and the French Riviera in the 1920s, creating the backdrop for his most widely-acclaimed work, *The Great Gatsby*, which was published in 1925. He like so many others befriended great authors such as Ernest Hemingway (1899-1961) during this period. Fitzgerald contributed stories to *The Saturday Evening Post* for most of his career, thereby receiving a steady income for this writing.

Fitzgerald and many others of the time were critics of society, including Sinclair Lewis, but relating to different aspects of American society with which they were dissatisfied. Hemingway saw violence and death first-hand as an ambulance driver in World War I, which influenced his style of writing and led to his award of the Nobel Prize for Literature in 1954. He was an iconic American author and journalist, who covered the Spanish Civil War, and lived life with gusto it seems, travelling greatly.

The poetry of Walt Whitman appears to be, on one hand, a re-statement of the existential nature of artistic expression found in Dickinson's approach, whilst on the other hand it is a wholly new grasp of modern being. His imagination is robust and heterogenic, pushing him more to national and ideological contexts, which are, however, also relevant realms for modernist poets. Whitman is one of those unique poets who tackles the most profound layers of humanity through more pragmatic (political, social, racial, industrial, and rural) realities. Given the differences, both have one thing in common – they are no longer traditional poets expressing traditional concerns through a traditional poetic language.

William Faulkner (1897-1962), another Nobel Prize winner (1949) and rival of Hemingway, spent most of his life in north-central Mississippi. Faulkner was surrounded

by stories, hearing his elders' account of the Civil War, slavery, the Ku Klux Klan, and his family history, spawning his interest in writing.¹⁷ As such, his writing and background were very different to most of the writers discussed above. John Steinbeck (1902-1968) was another American winner of the Nobel Prize (1962) with a very different background. He spent most of his life in California and his masterpiece, *The Grapes of Wrath*, tells the story of the migration of a poor and down-trodden Oklahoma-based family to California, themes that run through much of his work. He had very unreliable income sources and had to live at times on welfare payments, with financial support also from his family. Joyce Carol Oates (1938) is another New Englander and wrote with urban violent material, such as the Detroit riots, and the bleak blue-collar world of her youth in update New York. She was a journalist and author, like so many authors, held various academic posts, including since 1978 one at Princeton.

This period also witnessed the flourishing of American drama and its international reputation in this genre. Eugene O'Neill (1888-1953) was the son of an Irish immigrant and grew up in New York City, who was also awarded the Nobel Prize (1933). His most celebrated work, *Long Day's Journey into Night*, reflected an interest in those on the fringes of life he would have met in New York. Two other great American playwrights also lived in this period, Tennessee Williams (1911-1983) and Arthur Miller (1915-2015). Williams, born in Mississippi, later travelled widely in America and Europe, apparently for inspiration for his work. He proved to be a prolific writer and one of his early plays earned him a sizeable sum of money in a writing contest. More importantly, it landed him a publishing agent who would become his friend and adviser. Miller on the other hand was yet another American writer based in New York, his most famous work perhaps being *Death of a Salesman*. His work provided a voice for the white working-class Americans and resonates to this day.

As our data set ends with those born by 1949, and as many creative writers tend to be most productive between the ages of 20 to 40, then we are in effect talking mostly about those born between 1919 and 1949, some of whom have already been mentioned.

Post WWII saw the publication of some of the most popular creative writing in American history. Harper Lee's (1926-2016), *To Kill A Mocking Bird*, was published in 1960. Inspired by events in her hometown in Alabama, the book is about standing up for what is right in the context of endemic racist attitudes in the deep South.²⁰ Saul Bellow (1915-2005) was born in Canada but moved to Chicago in 1925. He had a long career in academia and won the Nobel Prize in 1976.²¹ He was one of the most influential novelists in this period, with his vivid pictures of life in an American city and the distinctive characters who inhabited them. J.D. Salinger (1919-2010) was raised in Manhattan, New York. Salinger published a story for the first time at the age of 21 when he met and befriended the founder and editor of the *Story Magazine* at Columbia University. His early stories were published here, but soon Salinger's work started making its way to more publications such as the *Saturday Evening Post* and *Collier's*. His experiences during action in WWII influenced greatly his most famous book *The Catcher in the Rye*. The autobiographic nature of the novel became the voice of a whole generation of young men wedged in frustration over the conventions of society and the perceived madness of the state-of-affairs in America.

America during the period under review produced not only great fiction but also fine poetry and drama. For playwrights being close to producing theatres was clearly very important, with New York city emerging as the major centre for drama in the 20th century, both Broadway and Off- Broadway. In contrast, there was no pressing need for poets to locate in any special place, except perhaps close to other poets, although some of them were isolates. Many of them though in the later periods had to earn an income from sources other than creative writing, relying greatly on writing for magazines and newspaper which also had locational implications. They also needed to have regular contact with agents and publishers,⁴⁰ with again the likelihood that they had to be in certain centres.

CONCLUSION

This paper though has provided a quite detailed statistical outline of, and basis for, aspects of US literary authors that were perhaps only understood in an anecdotal sense up to now. As such it may shape in some small way the literary criticism debate, as the opening

quotation indicated, and also provide another historical example of creative cities long being amagnet for creative workers.

REFERENCES

1. Andersson, Å. (2014). ‘Creative people need creative cities’, in Å. Andersson D. Andersson and C. Mellander, eds., *Handbook of Creative Cities*, Edward Elgar Cheltenham, 2011, pp. 14{55).
2. Baer, J. and J. Kaufman (2011), ‘Gender differences in creativity’, *Journal of Creative Behaviour*, 42 (2) pp. 75-105.
3. Benedek, M. Bruckdorfer, and E. Jauk (2019). ‘Motivations for creativity: exploring the whatand why of everyday creativity’, *Journal of Creative Behaviour*, pp. 1-16.
4. Kuld and O’Hagan (2019). ‘Location, migration and age: literary clusters in Germany frommid-18th to early-20th Century’, Dublin: TRiSS WP 2, Trinity College.
5. Lehman, H. (1953). *Age and Achievement*, Princeton: Princeton University Press.

